

Effect of some complex nutrients on improvement of bioaccumulation of lead by *Rhizopus arrhizus*

Sauryya Bhattacharyya^a, Tapan Kumar Pal^b and Arunabha Basumajumdar^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemical Technology, University of Calcutta, 92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : sauryya@hotmail.com; a_basumajumdar@vsnl.net Telefax : 91-33-23519755

^bDepartment of Biotechnology, Bengal Institute of Technology, On Basanti Highway, Hadia, Kolkata-700 150, India

E-mail : tapankpal@gmail.com

Manuscript received 19 September 2008, accepted 19 March 2009

Abstract : The present study indicated that a few complex nutrients enhanced bioaccumulation of lead by *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 from chemically defined medium containing 1 mg/L of the metal. Amongst them, yeast extract showed most prominent effect. Highly significant increment ($p < 0.001$) of lead accumulation of about 67% [from 147.8 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (control) to 247.78 $\mu\text{g/g}$ cell dry weight] was observed when the culture medium was supplemented with yeast extract at a concentration of 10 mg/ml. Specific composition of a complex nutrient was found to influence lead accumulation, when a commercial peptone preparation enriched with tryptophan showed improved bioaccumulation of lead, in comparison to other peptone. A few amino acids and water-soluble vitamins were also found to stimulate lead uptake in similar cultural conditions, although not to the extent of the complex nutrients. The present study indicated that lead removal from aqueous systems with the use of commercially available complex nutrients as composite sources of amino acids, vitamins and other useful macromolecules for *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1, would definitely provide cost-effectiveness when applied in large-scale industrial processes.

Keywords : Bioaccumulation, *Rhizopus arrhizus*, lead, amino acids, vitamins.

Introduction

The techniques for removal of heavy metals from water bodies are shifting from chemical absorbents to biosorbents, presumably due to the fact that heavy metals are such conservative pollutants that are unaffected by the natural biogeochemical cycling methods¹ and accumulate in the living bodies through food-chain². Among the biosorbents, microbe-based materials are attractive since they are naturally occurring, and the spent biomasses from fermentation or other industries can be utilized efficiently thus providing low operational costs³ and minimal formation of sludges to be disposed off⁴.

Many microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, algae and yeasts concentrate heavy metals at different capacities in inactivated or alive conditions^{5,6}. However, low binding capacities of inactivated/dead biomasses towards specific metals like nickel and failure to remove metals from actual industrial effluents due to the presence

of several inorganic and organic ligands limited this approach⁷. In such conditions, metabolically active, preferably metal-resistant microorganisms would ensure better accumulation of metals through a combination of processes like-bioprecipitation, metal adsorption in the cell-surface followed by metabolism driven uptake inside. These are all energy-dependent cellular activities, which need metabolic energy to be replenished by the use of appropriate macro- or micro-nutrients.

Rhizopus arrhizus, a common mold, was found to remove a few toxic heavy metals in a metabolism-dependent manner from aqueous culture medium in laboratory conditions⁸. The capacity of metal uptake, especially lead, could be increased when the mold was adapted to higher concentrations of the metal. Optimization of the components of the synthetic growth medium improved the degree of lead removal considerably⁹. In the present study, complex nutrient sources as a judicious consortium of

*Present address : Vice-Chancellor, University of North Bengal, Raja Rammohunpur, Darjeeling-734 013, West Bengal, India.

macro-nutrients (e.g. carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and sulfur) and micro-nutrients (e.g. trace elements) was supplemented to adjudicate any synergistic effect on metabolism-driven uptake of lead by the metal-adapted strain, *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1.

Results and discussion

In the present study, it was observed that several complex nutrients from plant and animal origin, as metabolic energy sources, exerted a significant improvement in lead bioaccumulation by *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of complex nutrients on bioaccumulation of lead by *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1
[Results are expressed as mean ($n = 4$) \pm SD]

Complex nutrient	Concentration (mg/ml)	Lead bioaccumulation ($\mu\text{g/g}$ cell dry weight)
[Control]	–	147.80 \pm 2.02
Malt extract	2.5	194.35 \pm 6.83 ^a
	5.0	216.30 \pm 4.51 ^a
	7.5	222.85 \pm 4.19 ^b
	10.0	213.28 \pm 3.85 ^b
	20.0	199.28 \pm 5.22 ^a
Yeast extract	2.5	194.35 \pm 6.83 ^a
	5.0	215.36 \pm 4.79 ^b
	7.5	224.60 \pm 3.89 ^b
	10.0	247.78 \pm 5.73 ^b
	20.0	231.28 \pm 5.78 ^b
Peptone (bacteriological) [enriched with tryptophan]	2.5	191.85 \pm 10.62 ^a
	5.0	209.05 \pm 3.20 ^b
	7.5	221.85 \pm 3.70 ^b
	10.0	215.03 \pm 4.22 ^b
Peptone M (mycological)	2.5	161.33 \pm 6.18 ^a
	5.0	177.06 \pm 5.71 ^a
	7.5	187.58 \pm 5.11 ^a
	10.0	195.93 \pm 4.28 ^a
	20.0	184.99 \pm 3.28 ^a
Meat extract	2.5	180.10 \pm 4.97 ^a
	5.0	194.05 \pm 5.62 ^a
	7.5	220.47 \pm 3.85 ^b
	10.0	214.03 \pm 4.73 ^b
Wheat-bran liquor	2.5	187.60 \pm 5.51 ^a
	5.0	198.30 \pm 4.23 ^a
	7.5	221.35 \pm 2.29 ^b
	10.0	206.53 \pm 3.99 ^b
	20.0	183.53 \pm 5.23 ^a

^a $p < 0.01$ and ^b $p < 0.001$, compared to control (One-way ANOVA).

Amongst the complex nutrients, yeast extract showed most prominent effect. Highly significant increment of lead accumulation of about 67% [from 147.8 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (control) to 247.78 $\mu\text{g/g}$ cell dry weight] was observed when the culture medium was supplemented with yeast extract at a concentration of 10 mg/ml ($p < 0.001$). It was also observed that complex nutrients of plant origin used in the present study showed significant improvement in the bioaccumulation potential of *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 in removing lead from culture medium, whereas only one (viz. meat extract) out of five complex nutrients of animal origin showed significant bioaccumulation of lead (Table 1). Meat extract, at a concentration of 7.5 mg/ml in the culture medium, removed lead in a highly significant manner ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1).

It can easily be perceived that the stimulatory effect of complex nutrients upon lead bioaccumulation by *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 might be due to the presence of a combination of amino acids, sugars, water-soluble vitamins and trace elements. All these components stimulated growth and metabolism of the mold so that the energy-dependent metal uptake mechanism was boosted up. Influence of a few complex nutrients, viz. rice-bran extract and corn-steep liquor on the growth of some filamentous fungi as well as on their metabolite production was observed by earlier workers in commercial set-ups^{10,11}. In the present study, it was also observed that not only the complex nutrients, but also specific composition of a complex nutrient influenced the lead accumulation capacity of *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1. The mold showed highly significant bioaccumulation of lead when a commercial peptone preparation enriched with tryptophan was used in the culture medium, in comparison to other peptone (Table 1). The result indicated the fact that aromatic amino acids might be useful for the mold during bioaccumulation. Using individual amino acids in the culture medium substantiated this. It was observed that aromatic amino acids showed significant removal of lead by the mold (Table 2). Amongst the aromatic amino acids, tyrosine showed the maximum stimulatory effect and lead accumulation increased significantly ($p < 0.01$) from 147.8 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (control) to 213.60 $\mu\text{g/g}$ (Table 2), when supplemented at a concentration of 1 mg/ml. This might be due to the effect of aromatic amino acids as precursors of coenzyme Q (CoQ), the essential metabolite of the energy-producing reactions in mitochondria.

dria. Several other amino acids, viz. glycine, leucine, proline, cysteine and methionine also showed significant stimulatory effect on lead bioaccumulation in comparison to control (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of amino acids on bioaccumulation of lead by *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1
[Results are expressed as mean ($n = 4$) \pm SD]

Amino acids	Concentration (mg/ml)	Lead bioaccumulation ($\mu\text{g/g}$ cell dry weight)
[Control]	-	147.80 \pm 2.02
Glycine	0.5	197.55 \pm 1.82 ^a
	0.75	212.35 \pm 1.73 ^b
	1.0	203.85 \pm 2.44 ^b
	2.0	188.93 \pm 1.40 ^a
Leucine	0.5	188.58 \pm 1.83 ^a
	0.75	201.20 \pm 2.50 ^a
	1.0	191.20 \pm 2.57 ^a
	2.0	175.18 \pm 2.46 ^a
Proline	0.5	195.65 \pm 2.30 ^a
	0.75	211.50 \pm 2.21 ^b
	1.0	199.48 \pm 3.10 ^a
	2.0	184.25 \pm 3.51 ^a
Phenylalanine	0.5	204.00 \pm 1.56 ^a
	0.75	210.78 \pm 1.85 ^b
	1.0	200.45 \pm 2.14 ^a
	2.0	187.45 \pm 2.79 ^a
Tryptophan	0.5	189.35 \pm 1.71 ^a
	0.75	201.05 \pm 1.41 ^a
	1.0	203.60 \pm 1.36 ^a
	2.0	196.28 \pm 2.09 ^a
Tyrosine	0.5	195.60 \pm 2.91 ^a
	0.75	207.55 \pm 2.12 ^b
	1.0	213.60 \pm 1.36 ^b
	2.0	196.28 \pm 2.09 ^a
Cysteine	0.5	174.68 \pm 3.14 ^a
	0.75	208.61 \pm 2.95 ^b
	1.0	220.54 \pm 3.62 ^b
	2.0	208.44 \pm 3.44 ^a
Methionine	0.5	179.38 \pm 1.48 ^a
	0.75	202.56 \pm 4.88 ^a
	1.0	222.66 \pm 3.27 ^b
	2.0	216.56 \pm 3.98 ^b

^a $p < 0.01$ and ^b $p < 0.001$, compared to control (One-way ANOVA).

A few water-soluble vitamins, viz. ascorbic acid, pyridoxine and nicotinic acid also showed significant ($p < 0.01$) stimulatory effect on lead accumulation by *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 (Table 3). This was in accordance with

Table 3. Effect of water soluble vitamins on bioaccumulation of lead by *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1
[Results are expressed as mean ($n = 4$) \pm SD]

Vitamins	Concentration (mg/ml)	Lead bioaccumulation ($\mu\text{g/g}$ cell dry weight)
[Control]	-	147.80 \pm 2.02
Ascorbic acid	5	178.65 \pm 3.57 ^a
	10	193.60 \pm 5.31 ^a
	15	199.23 \pm 6.96 ^b
	20	176.23 \pm 8.61 ^a
Pyridoxine	5	183.65 \pm 3.07 ^a
	10	195.35 \pm 3.59 ^a
	15	200.28 \pm 5.90 ^b
	20	177.73 \pm 8.76 ^a
Nicotinic acid	5	173.68 \pm 12.10 ^a
	10	192.85 \pm 10.81 ^a
	15	235.23 \pm 10.51 ^b
	20	177.48 \pm 10.90 ^a

^a $p < 0.01$ and ^b $p < 0.001$, compared to control (One-way ANOVA).

the fact that yeast extract, which is enriched with a number of water-soluble vitamins, showed most prominent stimulatory effect in the present study (Table 1). However, stimulatory effect of individual vitamins or amino acids on lead accumulation did not exceed the stimulatory effect of the complex nutrients, since synergistic effect of all these biomolecules would be essential for their proper functioning. Complex nutrients might provide such synergism.

The findings from the present study clearly indicated that complex nutrients enhanced bioaccumulation of lead by *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 from chemically defined medium fortified with 1 mg/L of lead. It was also observed that several amino acids and water-soluble vitamins stimulated lead uptake in similar cultural conditions. This can be perceived easily as amino acids and vitamins exert some important effects in the living system. However, use of vitamins and amino acids in large-scale industrial application of metal-removal processes would reduce cost-effectiveness of the process. The present study showed promising possibilities of lead removal from aqueous systems with the use of commercially available complex nutrients as composite sources of amino acids, vitamins and other useful macromolecules for *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1, which would definitely take care of the economical aspects when applied in large-scale industrial processes.

Experimental

All the chemicals, except the complex nutrients, were purchased from Merck or Loba (AR grade). Complex nutrients of best qualities were purchased from either CDH or Oxoid-Merck. A few complex nutrients, viz. rice-bran liquor, wheat-bran liquor, corn-steep liquor and paddy-soak liquor were prepared in the laboratory as described below. All the culture media preparation was done using double-distilled water.

Preparation of rice-bran liquor : 20 g of rice-bran (free from mud) was taken in 200 ml of warm distilled water. The suspension was kept at 55 °C for 18 h. The extract was filtered through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover the solid material.

Preparation of wheat-bran liquor : 20 g of bran (free from mud) was taken in 200 ml of warm distilled water. The suspension was kept at 55 °C for 18 h. The extract was filtered through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover the solid material.

Preparation of corn-steep liquor : 100 g of maize was taken in 250 ml of distilled water containing 0.52% potassium meta-bisulfite. The suspension was kept at 55 °C for 48 h. The extract was filtered through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover the solid material.

Preparation of paddy-soak liquor : 200 g thoroughly washed paddy was taken in 200 ml of distilled water and allowed to soak water for 2 h at 55 °C till the grain swelled completely. The soaked water was filtered through cotton and evaporated to dryness under vacuum to recover the solid material.

A high concentration of lead tolerant strain of *Rhizopus arrhizus* (viz. *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1) was developed and maintained as described previously¹². Composition of the synthetic culture media for metal uptake experiments as well as other culture conditions was also described¹². In the present study, complex nutrients were supplemented in the culture media in concentrations of 2.5, 5, 7.5, 10 and 20 mg/ml. Amino acids were supplemented at concentrations of 0.5, 0.75, 1 and 2 mg/ml and

the vitamins were supplemented at concentrations of 5, 10, 15 and 20 µg/ml. After desired period of incubation, the cell mass were separated by filtration, washed thoroughly with double distilled water, digested with 6 (N) HNO₃ and the lead content was analyzed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer¹². The amount of lead accumulated by the microorganism was calculated by calculating the biomass metal loading, according to a formula described elsewhere¹³.

All the data, in the present study, were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Dunett's post-hoc test for multiple comparisons of the treatment means. A *p*-value of 0.01 or less was taken as criteria for a statistically significant difference. All statistical calculations were done with the software – SPSS version 7.5.

References

1. J. C. Igwe and A. A. Abia, *African J. Biotechnol.*, 2006, **5**, 1167.
2. M. G. Mortuza, T. Takahashi, T. Ueki, T. Kosaka, H. Michibata and H. Hosoya, *J. Health Sci.*, 2005, **51**, 676.
3. B. Volesky, *Trends in Biotechnol.*, 1987, **5**, 96.
4. D. Kratchovil and B. Volesky, *Trends in Biotechnol.*, 1998, **16**, 291.
5. H. Doshi, C. Seth, A. Ray and I. L. Kothari, *Curr. Microbiol.*, 2008, **56**, 246.
6. K. Vijayaraghavan and Y. S. Yun, *Biotechnol. Adv.*, 2008, **26**, 266.
7. A. Malik, *Environ. Internatl.*, 2004, **30**, 261.
8. S. Bhattacharyya, T. K. Pal, A. Basumajumdar and A. K. Banik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 747.
9. S. Bhattacharyya, T. K. Pal, A. Basumajumdar and A. K. Banik, 'Proceedings of the Indian Chemical Engineering Congress (CHEMCON-2000)', Kolkata, 2000, BIOP-5.
10. H. W. Schroeder, *Appl. Microbiol.*, 1966, **14**, 381.
11. A. Sumantha, P. Deepa, C. Sandhya, G. Szakacs, C. R. Soccol and A. Pandey, *Braz. Arch. Biol. Technol.*, 2006, **49**, 843.
12. A. Basumajumdar, S. Bhattacharyya and T. K. Pal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 410.
13. A. Cabuk, S. Ilhan, C. Filik and F. Caliskan, *Turk. J. Biol.*, 2005, **29**, 23.